

LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE OF THE LANGUAGE AND ITS REFLECTION IN THE LANGUAGE

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Abstract: It is related to clarifying the linguistic and cultural understanding of a person in relation to his cultural and ethnic ideas about the world.

Key words: linguistic and cultural, ethnic idea, linguistic and cultural, linguistics, cultural studies, custom, tradition.

Linguistics emerged as an independent branch of linguistics in the 90s of the 20th century. According to the researchers, the term "linguculturalology" (Lat. lingua "language"; cultus "respect, bow"; Greek. "science, science") was coined by the Moscow phraseological school under the leadership of V.N. Telia (Y.S. Stepanov, A.D. Arutyunova, V.V. Vorobyev, V. Shaklein, V.A. Maslova) appeared in connection with the research.

If cultural science (culturology) studies the self-awareness of a person in his social and cultural life according to nature, society, history, art and other fields, linguistics studies the mental models of the linguistic landscape of the world that are reflected and recorded in language. studies the human worldview. The subject of linguculturalology is language and culture, which are in close contact with each other. Linguistics is a new field of language research formed at the intersection of cultural studies and linguistics. Lingvokulturology studies the relationship between culture and language, their interaction, and the manifestations of national culture reflected in language. Linguistics is closely related to ethnolinguistics and sociolinguistics. Even according to V. N. Telia, linguocultural science is a component of ethnolinguistics. However, both linguistic and cultural studies and ethnolinguistics are separate disciplines in their essence. The roots of ethnolinguistics began with W. Humboldt in Europe, F. Boas, E. Sepir and B. Whorf in America; In Russia, it goes back to the researches of D.K. Zelenin, Ye.F. Karsky, A.A. Shakhmatov, A.A. Potebnya, A.N. Afanasyev, A.I. Sobolevsky and others. V. A. Zveginsev described ethnolinguistics as a direction that studies the relationship of language with the social structure of society or the culture, traditions, and customs of the people. Lingvokulturology is inextricably linked with the following concepts.

It is known that the anthropocentric approach occupies a special place in the study of language units in the science of linguistics. According to this approach, the

"human factor" is one of the primary factors in the formation and development of language units. As a result of the development of this anthropocentric view, a number of new disciplines appeared in linguistics, including the science of linguoculturology.

Language is the most important way of forming human knowledge about the world. In the process of activity, the person defines the results of cognition in words, showing the objective world. The totality of this knowledge, reflected in the linguistic form, is called in different concepts "intermediate world of language" or "lexical representation of the world" or "linguistic model of the world" or "linguistic representation of the world". It is because of its prevalence that we prefer its last term. (Apresyan 1995: 6).

By the end of the 20th century, linguistics began to accept the hypothesis that "language is not connected with culture, but rather it is a tool that grows out of culture and expresses it." At the moment, language is a means of creation, development, preservation (in the form of texts) and its component of culture. Because material and spiritual works of culture are created through language. On the basis of this idea, linguo-culturalism, which has been formed for thousands of years, emerged as a new, special field of science in the 90s of the 20th century. Linguistics is a product of the anthropocentric paradigm in linguistics, which has been developing over the last decades. By the beginning of the 21st century, linguistic and cultural studies became one of the leading directions in world linguistics. Linguoculturology studies folk culture reflected and consolidated in language and discourse. First of all, he studies the myths, legends, customs, traditions, traditions, customs, symbols, etc. of a particular culture. These concepts are related to culture, and they are reinforced in the language in the form of household and food behavior.

N. Alefirenko characterizes linguoculturalism as follows: - linguoculturalism is closely connected with linguistics and cultural studies, it has a synthesizing feature; - the main attention of linguo-culturology is focused on cultural evidence explained in language; - Linguistics is a branch of linguistics, so its research results can be used practically in the process of teaching mother tongue and foreign languages; - the main directions of linguistic and cultural studies: a) linguistic personality; b) language is a system of semiotic embodiment of cultural values

Historically, the idea of the linguistic landscape of the world is related to the ideas of Wilhelm von Humboldt and the Neo-Humboldtians about the internal form of language, as well as the hypothesis of linguistic relativity or the linguistic determinism of Edward Sapir and Benjamin Whorf, whose basic rules are as follows: language determines its way of thinking defines. The surrounding world depends on the language in which thinking is carried out.

W. von Humboldt was the first to pay attention to the national structure of language and thought. He stated that "different languages are a unique organ of

thought and perception for a nation" (W. von Humboldt 1985: 324). W. von Humboldt considers language to be an "intermediate world" between thought and reality, while language contains a separate national worldview. The scientist emphasizes the difference between the concepts of "intermediate world" (German: Zwischenwelt) and "view of the world" (German: Weltbild). Humboldt's "intermediate world" is a static product of linguistic activity that determines a person's perception of reality.

Its unit is a "mental object" - a concept. The landscape of the world is a moving, dynamic entity that is constantly changing, because it is really formed by the interaction of language. Its unity is the speech act (W. von Humboldt 1984: 48). Thus, language plays a major role in the formation of both concepts: "Language is an organ that forms thought, therefore it plays a leading role in the formation of a person's personality, in the formation of a system of concepts in him, in the transmission of accumulated experience to generations" (W. von Humboldt) 1985: 78).

The term "linguistic picture of the world" (Weltbild or Weltbild der Sprache in German) was introduced into science by the German linguist Leo Weisgerber. Recognized as the most influential representative and leader in the field of linguistics, this specialist emphasized the active role of language in human thought and practice, saying that "language is not a product of activity (Ergon), but activity (Energy)" (Humboldt 1984: 70)) This position developing L. Weisgerber proposed a "powerful" approach to language learning, which includes discovery in the language of power, due to which it actively affects both the cognitive and practical activities of its speakers. A similar approach to language learning involves the study of language effects. In modern terminology, it can be interpreted as an approach aimed at studying the cognitive and pragmatic functions of language. L. Weisgerber identified these functions not from the linguistic landscape of the whole world, but from one of its aspects - idiotic (that is, a real existing sign system used in a certain society, at a certain time and in a certain place), which is clearly realized is to increase. language features in general). However, language integrates not only the view of the world, but also the whole world into its constituent parts. In other words, the image of the world constructed in a certain language is a synthesis of common knowledge about the world with idiots. The source of the first is objective reality, and the source of the second is a national view of it. L. Weissgerber commented on the "energetic" approach to the study of the lexical view of the world using the category "Worten der Welt", which literally means "to deceive the world". The ungodliness of the world (in other words, verbalization) involves dividing reality into certain parts through words. Languages differ not only in the number of words they contain, but also in their internal forms. And this, in turn, means that among different languages not only do

all languages divide the world into the same segments, but there is a qualitatively different quantitative symmetry

Leo Weisgerber also tried to solve the problem of the ratio of scientific and linguistic pictures of the world. Here he followed in the footsteps of the German philosopher and culturologist Ernst Cassirer, who believed that the scientist's work, among other things, in order to achieve it, it is necessary to liberate the language understood by the object of his research. E. Cassirer wrote: "...philosophical knowledge is forced above all from the chains of language and myth, it must remove the witnesses of human imperfection before turning thoughts into pure ether." (Cashier). Cassirer recognized the superiority of linguistic consciousness over scientific consciousness.

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